

**IS THE LYMPHOCYTE/ C-REACTIVE PROTEIN RATIO
RELATED TO LONG-TERM MORTALITY IN ACUTE
CORONARY SYNDROME PATIENTS?****Oguz Kılıç¹, Fatih Kahraman², Fatma Özpamuk Karadeniz³**¹Department of Cardiology, Karaman Training and Research Hospital, Karaman, Karaman, Turkey²Department of Cardiology, Kütahya Evliya Çelebi Training and Research Hospital, Kütahya, Turkey³Department of Cardiology, Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University, Karaman, Turkey**ABSTRACT**

INTRODUCTION: Atherosclerotic coronary artery disease (CAD) is one of the most common chronic diseases that cause mortality and morbidity in the world. Many risk models have been described so far in the estimation of mortality after CAD. In this study, we aimed to investigate the relationship between mortality and lymphocyte/C-reactive protein ratio (LCR) in patients with the acute coronary syndrome (ACS) in long-term follow-up.

METHODS: A total of 718 patients admitted to the emergency department of our hospital with chest pain and equivalent symptoms and followed up in the coronary intensive care unit with the diagnosis of ACS were included. LCR and other laboratory parameters of each patient were recorded. The patients were followed up for an average of 36 months and mortality was recorded. The relationship between LCR and long-term mortality was investigated.

RESULTS: Among 718 patients, 64 deaths were observed at 36 months of follow-up. Patients were divided into two groups: group 1 survivor and group 2 death group. LCR was found significantly lower in the death group ($p < 0.001$). In univariate analysis, age, CAD, creatinine, and LCR were found as significant predictors of mortality. All parameters were added to multivariable linear regression analysis and showed that age (OR: 1.094, 95% CI: 1.063-1.127; $p < 0.001$) and LCR (OR: 0.770, 95% CI: 0.621-0.956; $p = 0.018$) are the only significant predictors of mortality.

CONCLUSION: We found a significant relationship between LCR and mortality in ACS patients. It can be used in clinical practice because it is inexpensive, easy to apply, and has a stronger prognostic prediction in follow-up after ACS.

Keywords: Coronary artery disease, mortality, lymphocyte, C-reactive protein

INTRODUCTION

Atherosclerotic coronary artery disease (CAD) is one of the most common chronic diseases that cause mortality and morbidity (1). Approximately 17 million people die each year due to CAD (2). It is a multifactorial disease. The most common causes are obesity, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, lipoprotein metabolism disorders, smoking, sedentary life, and family history (3). According to the latest data from the World Health Organization; stress and poverty is also effective in the emergence and progression of CAD (4). With each passing day, the incidence and prevalence of CAD increase, and the chronic disease burden of countries increases. This causes additional financial burden. When considered in terms of cost-effectiveness; the mortality and morbidity management strategies of both WHO and national health organizations focus on stratifying the patient according to their risk and using a low-cost, rapid, specific, non-invasive, and predictive prognostic factor.

It is known that inflammation is one of the basic elements that play a role in the atherosclerotic process (5,6). Current studies suggest that vascular inflammation plays an important role in the initiation, progression, plaque instability, and eventual rupture of atherosclerosis (7). Inflammatory hematological parameters such as neutrophil, lymphocyte, monocyte, platelet, and C-reactive protein predict immunological counts. In particular, several studies have shown that the neutrophil/lymphocyte ratio (NLR), lymphocyte/monocyte (LMR) ratio, and platelet-lymphocyte ratio (PLR) are important in the prognostic assessment of coronary heart disease (8-10). The systemic inflammation index (SII) is a new inflammatory marker that combines NLR with platelet. It is emphasized that SII is more promising than NLR, LMR, and PLR (11,12).

Okugawa et al. reported that the lymphocyte/CRP ratio (LCR) can be used to predict prognosis in colorectal cancers (13). Chen K. et al. also showed that LCR is an independent factor affecting the occurrence and severity of CAD (14). Although lymphocyte and CRP levels are used separately in the evaluation of prognosis, the ratio of lymphocyte/CRP in cardiovascular diseases has not yet been determined. In this study, we aimed to investigate the relationship between mortality and LCR in long-term follow-up after acute coronary syndrome (ACS).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Our study is a retrospective, observational study. Approval was obtained from the local ethics committee. It was in line with the Declaration of Helsinki. A total of 718 patients admitted to the emergency department of our hospital with chest pain and equivalent symptoms and followed up in the coronary intensive care unit with the diagnosis of ACS were included. The clinical characteristics and laboratory data of the patients and long-term follow-up results were accessed from the hospital database and recorded. Patients were diagnosed with ACS according to the principles of the 4th universal definition of AMI as defined by the European Society of Cardiology (ESC) (11). Sepsis or local infection, major surgery, bleeding, aortic dissection, myocarditis, cardiomyopathy, acute pulmonary embolism, and stroke were excluded. In addition, patients

with missing data, those with only medical follow-up, and those with missing long-term follow-up were not included.

The admission venous blood samples were taken for total blood count, and CRP. Biochemistry parameters except CRP were taken after overnight fasting. Complete blood count values, kidney function values (urea, creatinine), lipid (Total cholesterol, HDL-C, LDL-C, TG) parameters, and C- reactive protein were recorded. The LCR of each patient was calculated. Mortality was recorded in the long-term follow-up. The relationship between LCR and long-term mortality was investigated.

Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyzes were performed using SPSS 25.0 (IBM SPSS Statistics 25 software (Armonk, NY: IBM Corp.)). Continuous variables were defined as mean \pm standard deviation, and categorical variables were defined as numbers and percentages. Kolmogorov Smirnov and Shapiro Wilk tests were used to determine the normal distribution. Independent samples t test was used when parametric test conditions were met for independent group comparisons and Mann-Whitney U test was used when parametric test conditions were not met. The difference between categorical variables was analyzed by Chi-Square analysis. Logistic regression (LR) analysis was used to find the predictors of in-hospital mortality in NSTEMI. Univariate analysis was performed in the first step. Independent variables found as statistically significant (p -value less than 0.05) and clinically important parameters were added to binary multivariable logistic regression.

RESULTS

The results of 718 patients with ACS were analyzed. In 36 months' follow-up, 64 patients died. The mean age of the patients who died was higher (65 (56-73) years, 77 (72-87) years, $p<0.001$). The female sex ratio (183 (28), 26 (40.6), $p=0.043$) and the incidence of CAD (111 (17), 4 (6.3), $p=0.030$) were statistically significantly higher in the living group (Table 1). There was no statistical difference between the two groups in terms of DM, HT, HL, and smoking (Table 1). In the group with death in long-term follow-up, Lymphocyte (2.2 (1.5-3), 1.6 (1-2.2), $p<0.001$) and LCR (0.54 (0.26-1.12), 0.19 (0.05-1.00), $p<0.001$) was lower. Additionally, WBC (9.4 (7.6-11.5), 13.2 (12.2-15.7), $p=0.001$), creatinine (0.90 (0.79-1.10), 1.04 (0.88-1.28), $p=0.002$), CRP (1.7 (0.5-5.1), 7.4 (2.4-20.2), $p<0.001$) was higher (Table 1). In univariate analysis, age, CAD, creatinine, LCR were found as significant predictors of mortality (Table 2). All parameters were added to multivariable LR and multivariable LR analysis showed that age (**OR: 1.094, 95% CI: 1.063-1.127; $p<0.001$**) and LCR (**OR: 0.770, 95% CI: 0.621-0.956; $p=0.018$**) are the only significant predictors of mortality.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of The Study Population

	Survivors (N=654)	Nonsurvivors (N=64)	P Value
Age (years)	65 (56-73)	77 (72-87)	<0.001
Gender (Female), n(%)	183 (28)	26 (40.6)	0.043
Smoking, N(%)	194 (29.7)	13 (20.3)	0.147
HT, N(%)	299 (45.9)	28 (43.8)	0.793
DM, N(%)	177 (27.1)	21 (32.8)	0.379
CAD, N(%)	111 (17)	4 (6.3)	0.030
HL, N(%)	195 (29.9)	24 (37.5)	0.204
CRD, N(%)	4 (0.6)	2 (3.1)	0.093
WBC (10 ⁹ /l)	9.4 (7.6-11.5)	13.2 (12.2-15.7)	0.001
HGB (mg/dl)	13.6±1.9	13.2±2	0.119
Neutrophil (10 ³ /L)	6.2 (4.3-8)	7.9 (6.7-10.4)	0.210
Lymphocyte (10 ³ /L)	2.2 (1.5-3)	1.6 (1-2.2)	<0.001
Platelet (10 ³ /L)	224 (193-271)	275 (196-356)	0.207
Triglyceride (mg/dl)	155 (115-208)	119 (109-187)	0.709
Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	197±97	193±60	0.733
HDL-C (mg/dl)	40 (34-53)	38 (35-58)	0.622
LDL-C (mg/dl)	117±41	110±40	0.182
Creatinine (mg/dl)	0.90 (0.79-1.10)	1.04 (0.88-1.28)	0.002
CRP (mg/dl)	1.7 (0.5-5.1)	7.4 (2.4-20.2)	<0.001
LCR	0.54 (0.26-1.12)	0.19 (0.05-1.00)	<0.001

Continuous variables were summarized as mean ± SD, categorical variables were summarized as count and percentages. **Abbreviations:** HT: Hypertension, DM: Diabetes Mellitus, CAD: Coronary artery disease, HL: Hyperlipidemia, CRD: Chronic Renal Disease, WBC: White blood cell, HGB: Hemogram, HDL-C: High density lipoprotein cholesterol LDL-C: Low density lipoprotein cholesterol, , CRP: C-reactive Protein, LCR: Lymphocyte to C-reactive Protein ratio.

Table 2. Independent Predictors of long term hospital mortality

Variables	Univariate analysis		Multivariable analysis	
	OR (95% CI)	p	OR (95% CI)	p
Age (years)	1.117 (1.083-1.151)	<0.001	1.094 (1.063-1.127)	<0.001
CAD	0.326 (0.116-0.916)	0.033		
Creatinine	1.459 (0.994-2.143)	0.054		
LCR	0.646 (0.499-0.836)	0.001	0.770 (0.621-0.956)	0.018

Abbreviations: CAD:Coronary artery disease, LCR: Lymphocyte to C-reactive Protein ratio.

DISCUSSION

This study is the first to investigate the relationship between in-long term follow-up mortality and LCR in ACS patients. According to the results of our study; LCR is a strong predictor of mortality at long-term follow-up after ACS.

Many studies are ongoing on the pathophysiology of coronary heart disease (CHD) (15). Especially in the last 20 years, it has been increasingly accepted that atherosclerosis is an active inflammatory disease (16). Inflammation plays an important role in the formation, progression, and rupture of atherosclerotic plaque (16). Neutrophil and platelet are cells of innate immunity while lymphocyte represents acquired immunity (17,18). In many studies, the effect of the immune system on prognosis was investigated by using neutrophil, lymphocyte, and platelet cells.

Studies have shown that increased early CRP levels can be used to predict long-term cardiovascular events in ACS patients (19, 20). In addition, hematological inflammatory parameters with low lymphocyte levels were found to be an independent predictor of prognosis in ACS patients (21). LCR is the ratio of lymphocyte count to CRP. Rather than evaluating lymphocyte and CRP separately, evaluating lymphocyte and CRP together may provide a better prognostic contribution. In a study, it was determined that high lymphocyte level and low CRP level had a protective effect on atherosclerosis (8). On the other hand, LCR can provide stronger prognostic information by reducing bias. To our knowledge, there is no prognostic study of LCR in cardiovascular diseases. The only cardiac study in the literature examined the relationship between LCR and CAD severity (14). In this study, low LCP level was found to be significantly associated with the severity of coronary artery disease. However, there are many studies in malignancy patients and it has strong predictive value in this patient group (22-24). In our study, we investigated the predictor of mortality of LRC in long-term follow-up after ACS. We found that LRC has a strong predictive value.

It was determined that the ratio of these hematologic inflammatory cells to each other (NLR, PLR, LMR, and SII) had a stronger predictive value in the cardiovascular area. NLR, PLR, and SII have been shown to correlate with the severity and prognosis of CAD. In a study conducted with 300 ACS patients in 2021, both PLR and NLR affected prognosis, and a positive correlation was found between the increase in the combination of PLR-NLR and the increase in major adverse cardiac events (25). In a meta-analysis published in 2018, NLR was found to be an indicator of hospitalization and long-term prognosis after interventional treatment in patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (26). In a study of 400 patients, SII was found to be an independent risk factor for the occurrence and severity of CAD (11). Furthermore, SII is a potential indicator for predicting clinical endpoints for elderly patients with ACS undergoing interventional treatment (27).

The limitations of our study; the results cannot be generalized due to the single-center study and the limited number of patients. Our study is not prospective. it is retrospective. Therefore, the results we have obtained should be supported by multicenter and large-participant prospective

studies. Some patients were excluded because of missing clinical data and/or laboratory variables. Finally, the presence of multiple comorbidities and vulnerabilities may affect in-hospital mortality.

In conclusion, our study is a study comparing LCR and in long-term follow-up mortality in ACS. In multivariate regression analysis, we found a significant relationship between LCR and in long-term follow-up mortality. It can be used in clinical practice because it is inexpensive, easy to apply, and has a stronger prognostic prediction in follow-up after ACS

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7676571

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